

All traits except length of sheath showed a wide range of phenotypic variation (see table). The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV). PCV ranged from 7.51 (days to 50% flowering) to 39.32 (tillers/plant). Culm angle, grains/panicle, leaf angle, and grain yield showed high GCV and PCV. The environmental coefficient of variability

(ECV) was higher for tillers/plant, yield/plant, culm angle, and grains/panicle, indicating that these traits were more susceptible to environmental factors than the other traits. Heritability ranged from 24.67 to 95.13%. High value for heritability was observed for days to flowering, plant height, 25-d-old seedling height, test weight, leaf angle, and panicle length. Low values were observed for

tillers/plant, grain yield, length of sheath, and length of leaf. The remaining traits showed moderate heritability.

Genetic advance in percent of mean was high for culm angle, grains panicle, leaf angle, test weight, seedling height, and plant height. Selection for these traits might be more effective than for the other traits. *ℳ*

Metroglyph analysis of lowland rice cultivars

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Morphological variations in 44 lowland rice cultivars were studied using score index and metroglyph methods. Index values of range of variability were partitioned into 4 groups using class intervals (see table). All traits except

yield and plant height, are represented by rays on the glyph (the rays for the same trait have the same position on each glyph). The performance of a particular genotype is denoted by its index score (see figure). *ℳ*

Indices of rice traits.

Character	Range of means	Score 1 Value<	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4 Value>
Days to flowering	104.33-133.00	111.49	111.49-118.65	118.66- 125.81	125.81
Internodes (no.)	4.27- 7.00	5.00	5.00- 5.500	5.51- 6.00	6.00
Tillers/plant	7.33- 25.60	11.89	11.89- 16.45	16.46- 21.01	21.01
Panicle length (cm)	22.43- 35.30	25.64	25.64- 28.85	28.86- 32.06	32.06
Grains/panicle	127.47- 335.60	179.50	179.50- 231.53	231.53- 283.56	283.56
Kernel length (mm)	4.47- 8.00	5.35	5.35- 6.23	6.24- 7.11	7.11
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.50- 2.37	1.71	1.71- 1.92	1.83- 2.13	2.13
Test weight (g)	11.83- 35.67	17.79	17.79- 23.75	23.76- 29.71	29.71

Variability of pigment in lowland rices of Uttar Pradesh, India

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Pigments traits in 5 plant parts were identified in 44 lowland cultivars, using I.S.I. India color chart.

Of 33 pigments found, kernel (K) had 13, grain (G) 12, node (N) 9, internode (I) 7, and leaf (L) 4 (see table).

Serial numbers were assigned to pigments:

- | | |
|---------------------------|------------------------|
| 1 = eau-de-nil | 18 = dark stone |
| 2 = sea green | 19 = portland stone |
| 3 = grass green | 20 = vellum |
| 4 = sage green | 21 = light straw |
| 5 = light bronze green | 22 = light biscuit |
| 6 = middle bronze green | 23 = champagne green |
| 7 = light brunswick green | 24 = sunshine |
| 8 = cypress green | 25 = berge |
| 9 = light olive green | 26 = light brown |
| 10 = steel furniture | 27 = middle brown |
| 11 = forest green | 28 = nut brown |
| 12 = deep cream | 29 = golden brown |
| 13 = light buff | 30 = orange brown |
| 14 = middle buff | 31 = light salmon pink |
| 15 = deep buff | 32 = chocolate |
| 16 = light stone | 33 = service brown |

The broad variability of kinds and distribution of pigments could be used to document cultivars, in genetic studies, as marker traits, and to incorporate desirable traits in breeding programs. *ℳ*

Scatter diagram of metroglyph analysis. List of cultivars: 1. Adamchini, 2. Anandi, 3. Bansfool, 4. Bansfore, 5. Bhainslote, 6. Bhedkabra, 7. Bhatafool, 8. Brahma, 9. Dato, 10. Deharadoon, 11. Derai, 12. Duniapat, 13. Foolbagan, 14. Gajraj, 15. Gauria A, 16. Gauria B, 17. Jilhore, 18. Kanakjiri, 19. Karinga, 20. Karingi, 21. Karanga, 22. Kesar, 23. Lakara, 24. Latera, 25. Lawangchur, 26. Lejura, 27. Madhukar, 28. Motibadam, 29. Ramkajara, 30. Rath, 31. Sahadeia, 32. Saro, 33. Selhi, 34. Sengar A, 35. Sengar B, 36. Silhat, 37. Shyamjira, 38. Sugapankhi A, 39. Sugapankhi B, 40. Sonachur, 41. Sorhi, 42. T-9, 43. T-100, and 44. Tulsifool.